

**KUPOSHANAJANYA VYADHI IN CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS TO
KARSHYA AND PHAKKA**Dr. Lokesh^{*1}, Dr. Nisha², Dr. Rohit Singh³¹Associate Professor and HOD, Department of Kaumarbhritya, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College and Hospital, Rewa (M.P.) India.²Associate Professor, Department of Shalaky Tantra, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College and Hospital, Rewa (M.P.) India.³Assistant Professor, Department of Kaumarbhritya, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College and Hospital, Rewa (M.P.) India.**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Lokesh^{*1}, Dr. Nisha², Dr. Rohit Singh³ (2026). Kuposhanjanya Vyadhi In Children With Special Emphasis To Karshya And Phakka. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(3), 327–329. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

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ABSTRACT

Children need proper nutrition to grow up healthy and develop normally. An adequate, balanced diet is necessary to avoid many common health problems. In India, malnourishment in children has caused many illnesses including infectious diseases. The ancient Ayurvedic literature refers to the nutritional disorders as *Kuposhanjanya Vyadhis*. There are many nutritional deficiency disorders under *Kuposhanjanya Vyadhis*. The ancient Ayurvedic texts provide a detailed description of different nutritional deficiencies, including *Phakka*, *Parigarbhika* and *Balashosha*. *Phakka Roga* is one of them which mean to have an emaciated body, which occurs because of lack of nourishment. Similarly Ayurveda provided description of *Phakka Roga* which refers to weakness or lack of vitality due to being very poor health condition associated with malnutrition. *Ayurveda* recommended *Brimhana* (nourishing) and *Rasayana* therapies along with easily digestible and nutritious foods to restore tissues. This article put special emphasis to *Karshya* and *Phakka Roga* under the umbrella of *Kuposhanjanya Vyadhi*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Karshya Roga*, *Phakka Roga*, *Kuposhanjanya Vyadhi*, *Malnutrition*.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda has classified malnutrition as *Aptarpajanjanya-Vyadhi* and *Santarpajanjanya-Vyadhi*. Poor nutrition affects child's physical growth and overall health status; therefore, it also affects their immunity. Furthermore, Ayurveda classified children suffering from malnutrition based on the severity and cause(s) into four categories as depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Various types of Kuposhanjanya Vyadhi.

Aahara is one of the three foundations of life as stated in Ayurvedic texts. In Ayurveda, a large amount of information has been documented about *Aahara*, making it a significant aspect of Ayurvedic medicine.

प्राणाः प्राणभूतामन्नमत्रं । (च. सूत्र 27)

अतश्च सर्वभूतानामाहारः स्थितिकारणम् ।

न त्वाहाराद् ऋते अस्त्य अन्यत् प्राणिनां प्राणधारणम् ॥ (का. खि. 4)

आरोग्यं भोजनाधिनम् । (का. खि. 5)

.....आहारो महाभैषज्यम् उच्यते ॥ (का. खि. 4)

Agni is an important principle of Ayurvedic medicine and represents the means by which food transforms into nourishment. The inappropriate *Ahara* or improper functioning of *Agni* may also leads disorders related to malnutrition.

आयुर्वर्णो बलं स्वास्थ्यमुत्साहोपचयौ प्रभाः ।
ओजस्तेजोऽग्नयः प्राणाश्वोक्ता देहनिहेतुकाः ।
शान्तेऽग्नौ स्त्रियते युक्ते चिरं जिवत्यनामयः ।
रोगी स्थद्विक्ते मूलमग्नितस्मान्निरुच्यते ॥(च.चि.15)

These disorders are characterized by low weight for height, wasting and a pale puffy face.^[1-3] These illness results impaired growth, delayed development and increase susceptibility towards the infectious diseases. This article further described Ayurvedic aspects of *Kuposhanjanya Vyadhis* with special emphasis to *Karshya Roga* and *Phakka Roga*.^[4-6]

PHAKKA ROGA

Phakka Roga refers to weakness or lack of vitality due to lack in quality of breast milk.

धात्री श्लैष्मिकदुग्धा तु फक्कदुग्धेति संज्ञिता ।
तक्षीरपो बहुव्याधिः काश्यात फक्कत्वमाप्नुयात् ॥(का. चि. 14)
And also the child of a mother who has had rapid consecutive pregnancies,
'गर्भिणीमातृकः क्षिप्र स्तन्यस्य विनिवर्तनात् ।

क्षीयते म्रियते वाऽपि स फक्को गर्भपीडितः ॥(का. चि. 14)

And a child who is in an orphanage without adequate parental care, a child suffering from *Grahani Roga*.

निजैरागन्तुभिश्चैव..... रो ज्वरादिभिः ।

अनाथः क्लिश्यते बालः क्षीणमांसबलदयुतिः ॥ (का. चि. 14)

Additionally, these children often have physical changes such as *Mandagni*, which prevents them from adequately creating *Rasa Dhatu*, preventing them from receiving nourishment through formation of *Dhatu*.

सप्तभिः देह धातरो धातवो द्विविध पुनः ।

यथास्वं अग्निभिः पाकं यान्ति किट्ट प्रसादवत् ॥ (च.चि.१५/१५)

Children in this condition also experience impaired digestion and absorption, further contributing to excessive urination and defecation, leading to nutritional depletion and consequently emaciation. The description of different types of *Phakka Roga* is explained in **Table 1**.^[3]

Table 1: Description of different types of Phakka Roga.

S. No.	Type of Phakka	Cause	Pathogenesis	Clinical Features
1	<i>Ksheeraja Phakka</i>	<i>Kapha</i> -vitiated milk, <i>Phakka Dugdha</i>	<i>Kapha</i> -vitiated milk causes obstruction in <i>Rasa Dhatu</i> circulation which leads improper nourishment of tissues causing progressive emaciation	Weakness, restricted movements, diarrhea, pneumonia and anemia
2	<i>Garbhaja Phakka</i>	Mother conceives again soon after delivery	Subsequent pregnancy reduces quality and quantity of milk leads inadequate nourishment and affects growth of child.	Weakness, growth retardation and delayed movements
3	<i>Vyadhija Phakka</i>	Chronic illness or recurrent endogenous/exogenous diseases, commonly seen in orphans or chronically ill children	Ongoing disease process causes <i>Dhatu Kshaya</i> which leads impaired nourishment and muscle wasting.	<i>Kshin Mamsa Bala Dhatu</i> , reduced strength and loss of skin luster

Treatment

If the lactating mother's breast milk is *Kapha*-vitiated, she must undergo *Shodhana* therapy prior to nursing her infant. Additionally, children should be given simple and nutritious foods. This is especially important when they are very young or newly weaned. If the mother has a *Nija* or *Agantuja* disease, then it must be treated. *Snehana* using medicated *Ghee* such as *Kalyanaka Ghrita*, *Shatpala Ghrita* or *Amrita Ghrita* suggested for mother. *Brahmi Ghrita*, herbal milk preparations with drugs such as *Madhuka*, *Punarnava*, *Eranda*, *Draksha* and *Trivrit* are advised for mother.^[6-8]

'कल्याणकं पिबेत् फक्कः षट्पलं वा यथाऽमृतम् ।
सप्तरात्रात् परं चैनं त्रिवृत्क्षीरेण शोधयेत् ॥

In *Kapha* predominant case, medicated milk and *Gomutra* would be given to the infant. When the infant is associated with *Vata* the *Vasti*, *Snehapana*, *Swedana* and *Udhvartana* are suggested. *Phakka Roga* can be managed by correcting the mother's digestion, providing her adequate nourishment, balancing the mother's

Doshas and providing treatment for any diseases affiliated with the mother.

KARSHYA ROGA

Karshya is a result of dietary, lifestyle, emotional, and intrinsic factors. *Ruksha Anna*, *Ruksha Aapana*, *Langhana*, *Pramitashana* and *Kriya Atiyoga* are contributing elements along with *Shoka*, *Chinta*, *Bhaya* and *Krodha*, etc. Other possible contributors to *Karshya* include *Atishrama*, *Atishmana*, *Ruksha Udarvatana* and *Vega Nigraha*. In addition to these factors, an individual's weight may be affected by their *Prakriti*, *Beeja Dosh*, *Jara* and *Vikara Anushaya*.^[4-6] In breastfeeding neonate there is *Vata* vitiated milk also responsible for *Karshya*.

विरसं वातसंसृष्टं कुशीभवति तत्पिबन् ।

न चास्य स्वदते क्षीरं कृच्छ्रेण च विवर्धते ॥(च.चि. 30)

Symptoms of Karshya

- ✓ *Shukra Swasthik* in buttocks, *Shushka Sphik* and *Udhara*
- ✓ *Dhamanijala Santate*

✓ *Twak-asthi Shesha and Ati Krusha*
 ✓ *Stoola Parva*
 शुष्कस्फिगुदरग्रीवो धमनीजालसन्ततः ।
 त्वगस्थिशेषोऽतिकृशः स्थूलपर्वा नरो मतः ॥ (च.सू. 21)

Samprapti of Karshya

If the *Agni* is impaired, then the toxins created after food is consumed are not processed properly either because of a weak *Agni* or a lack of *Rasa Dhatu*. *Rasa* has two elements: production & depletion. If either of these elements is disrupted, the body will not receive the nourishment needed to continue creating the other *Dhatu*s. When there is no nourishment provided to all the *Dhatu*s, this will result in an emaciation condition called *Karshya*.

Samprapti Ghataka is as follows.

- *Dosha: Vata Dosha*
- *Dushya: Rasa Dhatu*
- *Srotas: Rasavaha Srotas*
- Type of *Srotodushti: Sanga*
- *Adhishtana: Pakvashaya*
- *Vyaktisthana: Entire body*

If not treated or prevented *Karshya* can lead to numerous complications such as splenomegaly, respiratory issues, shortness of breath, distension/abdominal pains and *Grahani*, etc.^[5-8]

Management of Karshya

The primary method of treatment is *Brimhana* therapy; one should consume easily digestible, nutritious foods to restore tissues. An emaciated child should eat food such as old *Shali* rice, meat broth made from domesticated and wild animals, *Ghee*, milk, wheat and green gram, etc. Administering both *Rasayana* and *Brimhana* medicines will help to build up strength, provide nourishment to the body and eventually reverse the state of emaciation.^[8-10]

'गुरु शीतं मृदु स्निग्धं बहलं स्थूलपिच्छिलम् ।
 प्रायो मन्दं स्थिरं श्लक्ष्णं द्रव्यं बृंहणमुच्यते' ॥ (च.सू. 22:13)

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda explains the concept of malnourishment as consisting of both *Aptarpanajanya Vyadhi* (disorders associated with under-nutrition) and *Santarpanajanya Vyadhi* (disorders associated with over-nutrition) in children. Poor nutrition has a profound effect on a child's physical development, immune system, and overall development. The foundation for understanding this is made up of the principles of *Ahara* and *Agni*. Healthy tissues can be formed if digested and assimilated food is sufficient and *Agni* functions properly. If *Ahara* is insufficient or *Agni* is not working properly, then the tissues cannot be adequately nourished and conditions such as *Karshya* and *Phakka Roga* will result. The *Phakka Roga* results from a lack of nutrition from the mother's breast milk, recurrent pregnancies of the mother or a chronic health issue, manifesting in the child, as weakness, delays in growth, and wasting of the tissues.

Karshya Roga, is due to an improper diet, psychological issues and faulty metabolism, which result in the child being emaciated and experiencing systemic complications. In managing these two conditions, Ayurveda emphasizes correcting *Agni*, assuring the mother is healthy, providing appropriate nutrition to the child, balancing *Doshas*, and providing *Brimhana* and *Rasayana* therapies.

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